

IMPACT OF DIGITAL INDIA ON EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Digital education is a campaign launched by the government of India to work towards a new approach and to ensure education services are made available to students electronically by improved online infrastructure. This paper is mainly based on both primary as well as secondary data. Primary data is mainly collected from the educational sector mainly from lectures and students about how much they like digital technologies. Since changes are going on anyway, the great thing is to learn enough about them, so that we will be able to lay hold of them and turn them in the direction of our desires.

Keywords: Digitalization, Digital India, classroom, Brahmastra.

Introduction:

System consists of a set of rules, procedures, policies and processes. Every process gives us the output as products, services or sometimes both. These outputs may be tangible or intangible in nature. System controls and maintains the environment required for the required product or service manufacturing. Every product/service has a life cycle called Product Life Cycle. Similarly education system. To enhance the product or system for the next generation, compete in the future globalized market, for better innovations it is the need of the hour to improve our Education System. However, having said that, Digital India is not the Brahmastra for upgrading the Education System. It should be used as an added tool along with the basic learning tools and technologies.

Digitalization Education:

Digitalization education is a campaign launched by the government of India to work towards a new approach and to ensure education services are made available to students electronically by improved online infrastructure by increasing use of internet or by making education digitally empowered through technology

Objectives of the study:

- To understand and create awareness about the positive and negative impact of Digital India on education system.
- To create awareness about digital technologies in education.
- To educate people about digital India.
- To know the benefits of Digital technologies in education.

Research Methodology:

This paper is mainly based on both primary as well as secondary data. Primary data is mainly collected from educational sector mainly from lectures and students about how much they like digital technologies by collecting information through questionnaire. The secondary data is collected from websites related to digital technologies, journals, newspapers etc. And data are related to Bhatkal taluq.

Impact of Digital India on education system:

There are many impacts of Digital India on education system, but I will list only important ones.

Positive impacts:

1. Great accessibility to information
2. Develops Inquire based learning
3. Develops Problem based learning
4. Develops Project based learning
5. Great exposure
6. Reduces the cultural gap and removes the boundary

Negative Impacts:

1. Information Authenticity - Getting confused with the right and wrong information's due to information authenticity.
2. Copyrights issue – Unknowingly one can be culprit, just by copy and paste.
3. Irrelevant advertisements will derail your info hunt.
4. Data security – Root cause of next world war is not because of land, water, power or any other greediness. It's just because of data infiltration.

5. Single point of failure rate is very high as we dependent too much on Digital technologies.

Advantages of Digital India on education system:

There are many advantages of Digital India on education system in Bhatkal taluq, but I will list only important ones.

1. **Scalable:** Digital India enables us to quickly create and communicate new policies, training, ideas, and concepts. Be it for entertainment or formal education, Digital India is nimble.
2. **Capacity and Consistency:** Using Digital India allows educators to achieve a great degree of coverage for their target audience, and it ensures that the message is communicated in a consistent fashion. This results in all learners receiving the same training.
3. **High Learning Retention:** Blended learning approaches result in a higher knowledge retention rate. It also helps that coursework can be refreshed and updated whenever needed.
4. **Time and Money Savings:** This one is pretty well known, and a staple of any well-done Digital India program. Digital India reduces time away from the workplace, eliminates the need for travel, and removes the need for classroom-based training.
5. **Activity and performance measurement:** If you are using a learning management system to deliver your Digital India, then tracking learner progress is a piece-of-cake, and reporting on this activity is just as simple.
6. **Reduction of carbon foot print:** By leveraging Digital India for online testing and quizzing, the need for printing out paper-based assessments is reduced in fact it's practically eliminated altogether.

7. **Flexible:** Using Digital India, you can give employees and students the freedom to learn at their own convenience, and at a pace that is right for them. Staff can be trained in remote locations and in a consistent fashion as anyone receiving on-site training.

Digital Technologies on Education System:

Digital India on education system, can be made powerful and successful by implementing below digital technologies,

1. **Visual presenter:** visual presenter is also called as digital camera. Visual presenter is also one of the parts of digital technologies. It is teaching tool that allows student and teacher to show and share their view of lots of information to the whole class
2. **Video projector/interactive video projector:** a video projector is a projector that receives the video signals and shows the particular image on the screen of the projector by using the lens system. It projects the image through the video projector by using very high bright light. This digital technology is used for many applications such as classroom training, conference presentation, concerts etc.
3. **Tablet:** the original name of the tablet is Tablet computer the short name of this is Tablet. It is very thin and also flat mobile display tablet is totally taken with sensor including digital camera accelerometer and micro phone. By using the tablet with the internet connection we can learn any difficult subject also easily.
4. **Computer:** In modern generation computer become a part of our life. It is also become a very important tool in education system. The educators till today not ready to accept technology as their work partner. They feel shy to accept technology. But it is very useful to the educator to share their views about a specific subject the knowledge received through this will be long lasting in the minds of the learners or viewers
5. **Providing teachers and principle with laptops:** laptops and desktop now become important part of education. By providing laptop to the teachers when teaching become very easy. They used their laptops by connecting to the smart board to teach

their students. Teachers can save their knowledge and their views about particular subject into the Laptop.

6. **Satellite connected class room:** Satellite connected classrooms means the classroom computer is connected with the satellite, through the satellite connection by searching any particular topic that will be appear on the computer screen
By using satellite connection in education system we can learn each and everything about the subject easily searched topic about particular subject is directly displayed on screen from internet through satellite connection.
7. **Ensuring schools have high-quality infrastructure with WIFI campus.**
8. **Helping teachers to connect and network with each other online with the Virtual Learning Network.**
9. **Developing digital resources for school such as e-books.**

Digital Tools used in Bhatkal taluq:

1. Smart class

The concept is simple. A server is setup inside the school loaded with digital instruction and assessment materials mapped to school curriculum classrooms are wired to the server and are equipped with a state of art of digital teaching system (DTS) comprising of a highly versatile and interactive board and sophisticated projection system. Teacher access the digital contents in their classroom sessions and explain concept with the help of animation, graphics, videos etc.

2. Power point:

Power point is one of the important slide presentation software, now a days it is very useful tool in education system. Through the slide presentation learning concept become easy especially in large classes.

3. Educomp

There is a big innovation after 2003 in education sector is Educomp. It was a paradigm shift that did what no one had thought of before bring technology into classroom. It empowered teacher with well research mapped to curriculum digital modules which could project right in the classroom to elucidated and explain concepts.

4. TATA smart class

TATA Smart class started in 1990 in an interactive system targeting schools in Bhatkal taluq through innovative, interactive educational program that address the learning exceptional students as well as average students.

Findings of digital education:

Response regarding digital education in Bhatkal taluk

Questions	Offender reaction	
	Yes	No
1) Do you want to develop in digital technologies	65%	35%
2) Are you aware of digital technologies	85%	15%
3) Are you connected with the digital technologies	72%	28%
4) Are you agree with this technology will help in education system	95%	5%

From the above table shows that most of the students and teachers are using digital technologies and their response towards digital technologies is positive. From this study I can realize that in future digital technologies becoming one of the main part of education system in Bhatkal taluk

- 65% of students and teachers want to develop the digital technology in bhatkal and 35% of they do not want to develop the digital technologies
- 85% of students and teachers are aware about the digital technology
- Students and teachers are aware agreed with technology is 95%
- Certain students and teachers are not ready to adopt digital technology

Suggestion:

- ✓ Digital India should be implemented along with the traditional learning methodologies in the education system.
- ✓ Writing is one of the best and natural powerful creativity tool and it should be preserved from the storm of Digital India.

- ✓ With the lightening of speed of market competition Digital India is need of the hour with extra precautions.

Conclusion:

It is not the strongest of the species that survive nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change. Since changes are going on anyway, the great thing is to learn enough about them, so that we will be able to lay hold of them and turn them in the direction of our desires. Conditions and events are neither to be fled from nor passively acquiesced in they are to be utilized and directed.

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